

AN INTRODUCTION TO UBIQUITOUS COMPUTING IN THE MILITARY NETWORK

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Abstract: Ubiquitous computing analysis represents an emerging area that implements communication technologies in day-to-day life actions. Ubiquitous computing changes the methods in which people use computers, considering these are involved in everyday aspects. In ubiquitous computing, several types of processes operate automatically in the background and communicate on the user's account. The ubiquitous computing theory is to provide any information for everyone at anytime and anywhere instantly. Mobile ad-hoc Networks are currently a growing technology for the next generation of wireless communication networks. A mobile ad-hoc network can portray as a military or rescue operation network in which a set of mobile nodes are used to send out a mission operation in diplomatic terms. This paper presents common architecture principles of universal systems and analyses significant features in context-aware ubiquitous systems. The main purpose of this work is to define a principle for researchers who are new to ubiquitous computing and want to gain depth on analysis and implementation of a novel method for the ubiquitous computing system in military sectors, in order to contribute towards further research regulations expected into the quality-of-service pledge of ubiquitous computing. The ubiquitous computing is the future of technology related to the internet or smart devices. Moreover, the applicability of technologies found in smartphones, smart TVs and sensors can guide to an increase in strategic capabilities, like sensing and detecting, exchanging and sharing unique real-time data in the military field. This study aims to sketch particular methods by which the learning and teaching methods can be improved. The intelligence of technology advanced in the military sectors along with ubiquitous computing providing a rise in optimization, security, and defence.

Keywords: ubiquitous, pervasive computing, Mobile Ad-hoc network (MANET), Military sectors.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ubiquitous computing started to develop in the form of “live boards” that replaced chalkboards making its appearance also in other devices. By using building boards and by integrating them with other tools, researchers can better understand the basic model of ubiquitous computing. In trained circles of people, the “Ubiquitous Computing” term is generally used to define the ubiquitous information and communications technology (ICT) infrastructure proposed at short and medium-term solutions. Ubiquitous computing is less observed as a discrete domain of technology, but preferably as an emerging application of ICT that is developed into the everyday world [22]. Ubiquitous computing is hence a similar paradigm to virtual reality, which is known to foster learning methods.

Ubiquitous computing includes smart environments that support various activities of individuals. Representing ubiquitous computing is not as simple as describing a new kind of computer with more abilities than its ancestors. It is as complex as defining a new process of socializing, accessing data, communicating, playing, a completely new way of living [1].

A mobile ad-hoc network is established as a decentralized network without any infrastructure, containing mobile nodes that depend on each other's traffic activities. Mobile ad-hoc network (MANET) is a totally peer-to-peer network without any structure of centralized authority [27]. Interested people can be connected by their personal digital assistant (PDA) or laptop and they will depend on each other to stabilize connections and security assistance.

The paper is organized as follows: Section I presents the related work, Section II discusses the role of the mobile ad-hoc network computing in the military sector, Section III explains MANET's security-related data, Section IV presents details on ubiquitous computing, Section V discusses about the pervasive computing system.

II. RELATED WORK

Ubiquitous computing applications will have a visible influence mainly on institutions and societies. Ubiquitous computing has developed to such a level that its implementation covers a wide range: from smart devices all the way to self-driving transports. Typical applications include education, commerce, healthcare, and smart home. Applications in ubiquitous computing with military high-performance computing include laboratory scenes, manufacturing, emergency care, crime prevention, social games, logistics, and internet messaging [13] [7] [23] [24].

Security trials exist in several types of networks such as mobile ad-hoc networks, sensor networks, software-defined networks and the internet. The operations done so far on the security methods for multicast routing protocol of mobile ad-hoc network distributed are based on two constituents: attacks from unicast routing along with multicast-specific attacks and advanced solutions such as modifications in the protocol and more systems for security innovation [26] [28]. Mobile ad-hoc networks (MANET) have been bringing a lot of research attention for many years now, providing valuable data, forwarding protocols in these networks. Securing link availability and network stability have been analysed as well [8] [9]. Several mobile ad-hoc networks (MANET) protocol investigations still apply basic simulation models with limited or no significance to the real-world applications, referred for mobile ad hoc networks. To simplify the transferability in the real world, it is necessary to perform robust and realistic simulations of real-world situations for the evaluation of protocols [18].

III. MOBILE AD-HOC NETWORK IN MILITARY

The military fight technique in the 21st century became a digitalized cooperative organization tactic which depends profoundly on the different systems providing real time information. Applications of ubiquitous computing and network technologies in military defence is essential; it consists of a shared medium which is deeply demandable for radio communication applied in the war conditions. The mobile ad-hoc network is a necessity for creating a consistent ubiquitous network, used to structure a wireless network among the communication nodes, excluding the use of routers in the cable network. Each node should be implemented with functions for both servicing communication and operating as a router for the communication between the other nodes. There are applications of the mobile ad hoc network in the commercial market, military, and private sectors. Mobile ad-hoc networks provide users with access to share data despite their geographic location or proximity to infrastructure. In contradiction to the infrastructure networks, all nodes in the mobile ad-hoc networks (MANETs) are portable, and their connections are useful. Currently, in the military field there is a computer device implemented. Mobile ad-hoc networking would authorize the military to take advantage of conventional network technology to control an information network connecting the soldiers, vehicles, and military base headquarters [2] [17].

Security-related data collection for an attack detection in the mobile ad-hoc network (MANETs) becomes critical to assess and measure the real-time security of the mobile ad-hoc network and construct the network's response accordingly. It is secure to integrate several detection tools that can be considered as the second line of defence to detect attacks in the mobile ad-hoc networks. Usually, in most attack disclosure mechanisms, it is necessary to collect security-related information for further analysis. If security-related data collection is unreliable, attack detection and security measurement are forced to be disabled. Principally, untrustworthy security-related data collection will lead to suspicious detection results and incorrect security measurement [25].

IV. MANET'S SECURITY RELATED DATA

In this section, there are explained some threats that might exist in the security-related data collection, and as well propose requirements following trustworthy security-related data collection. In any detecting device, if the collected security-related data for identifying an attack fail to realize a real-time local scenario or are not enough to provide the accuracy of detection, the detection inquiry yields an unreliable result, which disables the real-time security measures of MANETs. Hence, it should be assured that the security-related data produced by a data provider entirely reflect the real-time local framework. This data provider transfers the data to a detector also known as data collector securely in a steady manner [14] [20].

The precision of attack detection and security measurement supremely confide on the trustworthiness of security-related data. A data provider might provide with incorrect data due to some circumstances like a hardware failure. The incorrect data might be provided intentionally: compromised data provider often gives incorrect data in order to avoid being discovered. In several detection mechanisms, an accurate detection output provided by a detector, certainly a source or a node, can trigger the effect mechanism of networks [6] [10].

The confidentiality of data should be secured, particularly in an unfriendly condition. Some encrypted security-related data should not be exposed to any unauthorized group of people, since an attacker strives to employ the gathered sensitive data to launch future attacks [15].

V. DETAILED EXPLANATION OF UBIQUITOUS COMPUTING

Ubiquitous computing is a theory where computing is initiated to rise universally using any device, in any location and any arrangement [11]. In ubiquitous computing, the computation conditions are secured. With developments in the computer science and technology field, computer software is seamlessly combined into people's daily lives. The devices work in the network as standalone devices with the main function being the communication with the human and with the other devices in the network. These devices promote context-aware applications, roaming users, location-aware co-operation, and mobile data access. Ubiquitous systems render access to data anywhere and anytime, and to multiple services while making the appearance of the system "invisible" to the user [16].

The three main properties for ubiquitous computing systems are distributed computation, invisibility, and context-awareness. The distributed computation indicates that the systems require to be networked, distributed and transparently friendly. The invisibility property means that the computer interaction with humans needs to be more isolated. Finally, context-awareness signifies the optimization of the system's performance in a mechanical and human environment; therefore, it is essential to make the systems aware of environmental context. The primary goal of ubiquitous computing is to be user-centric and to enable users to communicate with the system in a usual and non-intrusive way [12]. Ubiquitous computing's purpose is to serve users in daily activities.

VI. PERVASIVE COMPUTING SYSTEM

As in any software engineering field, experimenting pervasive computing applications is essential. However, this field has particular obligations that restrict generic testing tools from implementing ubiquitous computing applications [21]. The universal computing applications communicate with the users and with the physical environment. Generic software testing devices do not cope with either the simulation of the physical environment or the simulation of users in this physical environment. Facing these requirements makes the testing of pervasive computing applications challenging. In fact, there are only a few evolving approaches in the pervasive computing field; existing development proposes often understand that the system is somewhat or entirely useful [4].

However, implementing a widespread computing application for testing purposes can be costly and time-consuming, because it is expected to acquire, test, and configure all types of

equipment and software components. Furthermore, some situations are challenging to examine because they require unusual circumstances such as natural disasters. When no consideration layer is presented to the developer, the application code installs distributed systems operations, generating dependencies to the underlying technology and obscuring the code [5].

The pervasive computing (figure 1) is more environment-centric rather than web-based or mobile. The data obtained by the pervasive environment will be connected by the middleware software and the product will be created based on the existing environmental data [3].

Figure no. 1. Pervasive computing

VII. Conclusions and Future Work

Ubiquitous computing is a method of improving the computer usage by having computers accessible throughout the physical conditions but making them effectively transparent to the user. It is continuously transforming the way people live and interact. Today, ubiquitous computing is nevertheless a conception of technology. The paper presents the evolution of ubiquitous computing in time and analyses different features in context-aware ubiquitous systems. In this paper, it was discussed the vital role of mobile ad-hoc network (MANET) in the military sector, MANET representing a robust network which does not need the assistance of any fixed infrastructure. The hosts (nodes) in MANET are self-configurable and portable. Every node can work as a router to pass data to its destination. This study sketched several methods of ubiquitous computing, methods through which even the learning and teaching methods can be improved. As future work, it will be implemented a ubiquitous learning system for detecting, exchanging and sharing different types of real-time data in the military field.

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